

CRISIS PREPAREDNESS: ASSESSMENT OF ACTIVE SHOOTER TRAINING

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ABSTRACT

This paper critically assessed the three (3) activities of the campus active shooter workshop and drills exercise dated 25 August 2022, 25 May 2023, and 28 September 2023, respectively, at the University of the Philippines Los Baños (UPLB). The goal is to practice the coordination and communication if confronted with an active shooter or any shooting incident scenario inside the campus. The purpose of this study was to determine the perception of the participants, problems experienced in both discussion and operations-based exercises, strategies used in the implementation of emergency action exercises, as well as the learning impact of the participants. The methodology employed in this paper borrows from the homeland security exercise and evaluation program by the United States Department of Homeland Security (2020). The study revealed a predominance of male participants, particularly in administrative roles, across all activities, participants expressed satisfaction with the events and provided constructive feedback for improvement. The training workshop was commended for its clarity and relevance, while the active shooter workshop and simulation drills were praised for their objectives and organization. Suggestions for enhancement included improving psychological training, and conducting more simulations and awareness sessions. Overall, participants found these experiences valuable for enhancing preparedness for real-life scenarios. Findings of this study will provide useful information to the campus administrators the need to review the existing policies, training, drill, and exercise programs, to improve the overall security posture of their institution.

Keywords: *Active Shooter, Campus, Training*

INTRODUCTION

On the 24th of July 2022, a man shot three people in a supposed joyous graduation rite for the law students at Ateneo de Manila University; although the gunman was arrested, the incident resulted in the death of three people and one injured student (Gavilan, 2022). Mindanao State University also heightened its security measures after a shooting incident on the 14th of September 2021 occurred at the university's commercial center, killing two of their students and the assailants were onboard a motorcycle (Jerusalem, 2021).

In these two incidents in the past, the UPLB campus decided to conduct an active shooter workshop and actual drill exercise to address the readiness and response measure with the possibility of an armed assailant entering the campus. These preparedness activities should be based upon a risk assessment of the crisis events and protocols of response to ensure appropriate response to be incorporated in the campus's crisis management plan or manual. It is for this reason that other campus should organize the same to counter the possibility of an active shooter and enhance more on preparedness.

Active Shooter Training on UPLB Campus

On the 25th of the August 2022, the campus held active shooter preparedness webinar and invited three (3) resource persons. The first speaker, Atty. Kristoffer James E. Purisima, a former Office of Civil Defense deputy administrator, discussed the national government response policies on active shooter and shooting incidents. The second speaker was Capt. Sherhannah S. Paiso, a military professor and psychologist of the Armed Forces of the Philippines, discussed an active shooter's psychology and pre-attack behavior. According to her, statistics of campus shooting: mass shootings in the United States (US) from 2018 to 2021 with a total of 277 incidents. 73% of attacks, one or more students and faculty were killed. Leading causes of campus shootings: 87% bullying, 15% side effects from psychiatric drugs, 10% medication non-compliance. On the other hand, Retired Major General Leocadio SC. Santiago, Jr., tackled how to prepare and respond to an active shooting situation. Gen. Santiago is a former director of operations of the Philippine National Police. He belonged to the Philippine Military Academy Class of 1979 and is the current dean of the College of Criminology of the Philippine Christian University. (Tirones, 2022)

On the 25th of May 2023, it was the continuation of the activity and this time a table top exercise (TTX) was conducted. This TTX aims to practice coordination and communication if confronted with an active shooter or shooting incident scenario inside the campus. The exercise is divided into three (3) modules. The focus should be on identifying suggestions and recommended actions from the experts for improving preparedness, response and recovery efforts. The first module, operational on-scene security, first responder, and law enforcement coordination has the goal of assessing the participant's ability to establish an effective command structure that integrates all critical stakeholders to ensure efficient coordination in responding to and recovering from an active shooter incident. The second module, emotional support and psychological first aid

is to assess the participant's ability to provide emotional support services, including psychological first aid during the response to and recovery from an active shooter incident. The last module pertains to public information and recovery operations, the goal is to assess the participant's ability to deliver coordinated, actionable and timely information to critical partners and stakeholders and assess their recovery plans in the aftermath of an active shooter incident.

After the success of its webinar session and tabletop exercise on campus, an active shooter was used, followed by an actual simulation. On the 28th of September 2023, the last activity this time is the actual simulation or the actual active shooter drill on the campus. It was divided into three scenarios: first, three unidentified individuals enter the campus and open fire; second, hostage negotiation with the police using strategic tactics to help in the hostage negotiation process; and third and last, media handling and recovery phase wherein the campus administrators assure the public that everything is now under control. (Matalog, 2023)

Research Questions

To understand the perspective of the participants if the training objectives clearly defined and if the topics covered are relevant or interesting. The following are the research questions:

1. How would you rate the quality of the active shooter preparedness seminar?
2. How did you find the design of the lecture materials or modules?
3. How would you rate the way the active shooter simulation exercise is organized and delivered?
4. Overall, how would you rate your overall learning experience?
5. Do you have any suggestions that would make the training workshop better?

METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed in this paper borrowed from the Homeland Security Exercise and Evaluation Program (HSEEP) by the United States Department of Homeland Security (US-DHS). The HSEEP includes a common methodology for exercises across all mission areas. The methodology enables organizations a shared understanding of program development, conduct, evaluation, and improvement planning and fosters exercise-related interoperability and collaboration. HSEEP uses a common approach for planning, conducting, and evaluating individual exercises.

According to Renger (2009), a hybrid exercise is designed to assist exercise players in building their confidence in moving from discussing plans into testing plans and carrying out operations. It combines elements of both types of exercises with the purpose of creating a smoother transition from discussion-based to operations-based exercises.

Below is the timeline diagram for the activity.

Figure 1. Author’s conceptual framework from training to policy development

Discussion-Based Program Development

Using the HSEEP (2020) of US-DHS, the discussion-based exercises include seminars, webinars, workshops, tabletop exercises and games. This type of exercise focuses on strategic, policy-oriented issues, and facilitators or presenters lead the discussion, keeping participants moving towards meeting the exercise objectives. The following tables provide the information for the two types of discussion-based exercise:

Webinar Title:	Webinar on Preventing and Preparing for an Active Shooter and Shooting Incident inside the Campus
Element	Considerations and Activities
Purpose	To provide a good starting point to understand the principles and concepts of handling active shooter and shooting incident inside the campus
Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 subject-matter experts were invited

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • web-based seminar, an online presentation
Participant Goals	To understand the principles and concepts of handling such a situation
Outcome	After Activity Report (AAR)

TTX Title:	Campus Active Shooter Workshop and Table Top Exercise
Element	Considerations and Activities
Purpose	To generate discussion of various issues regarding principles and concepts of handling active shooter and shooting incident inside the campus
Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 subject-matter experts were invited • scenario is presented to describe an event at a simulated time • problems are discussed as a group and each will provide a resolution • discussion led by a facilitator
Participant Goals	To enhanced general awareness of each roles and responsibilities regarding protocol and response of handling such a situation
Outcome	AAR

Operations-Based Program Development

Operations-based exercises include drills, functional exercises, and full scales exercises, it include a real-time response such as initiating communications or mobilizing personnel and resources:

Drill Title:	Simulation Drills and Exercise on Campus Active Shooter Response
Element	Considerations and Activities
Purpose	To validate actual response and procedures of handling active shooter and shooting incident inside the campus
Structure	Clearly defined plans, procedures, and protocols need to be in place
Participant Goals	To practice coordination and communication when confronted with an active shooter or shooting incident inside the campus
Outcome	AAR

RESULTS

This chapter discusses the findings after data gathering on the case of the evaluation on the discussion-based and operations-based in response to active shooter incidents

Table 1. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	63	77.8%
Female	16	19.8%
Prefer Not to Say	2	2.4%
Total	81	100%

The demographic profile of the respondents in this study reveals a predominance of male participants, comprising 77.8% of the total sample. Female respondents represented a smaller proportion at 19.8%, while a minority chose not to disclose their sex, accounting for 2.4%. This distribution suggests a gender disparity in the respondents' composition, with males being significantly more represented than females. Such demographic insights are crucial for understanding the sample characteristics and potentially interpreting the findings of the study. It's important to note that while this study may have limitations in terms of representativeness, the data still provides valuable insights into the perceptions and experiences of individuals involved in the evaluation of discussion-based and operations-based exercises in response to active shooter incidents.

Table 2. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of job title

Job Title	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Faculty	9	11.1%
Researcher	5	6.2%
Admin	55	67.9%
Contractual	12	14.8%
Total	81	100%

The demographic profile of the respondents in this study reveals a diverse representation of job titles within the surveyed population. Among the participants, the majority, comprising 67.9%, held administrative positions, indicating a significant presence of administrative staff within the sampled group. Following closely, faculty members constituted 11.1% of the respondents, indicating a notable presence of academic staff in the study. Meanwhile, researchers accounted for 6.2% of the participants, suggesting a smaller yet still notable presence of individuals engaged in research activities. Additionally, contractual workers made up 14.8% of the respondents, representing a segment of the workforce with temporary or project-based employment arrangements. This distribution underscores the varied professional backgrounds and roles of the individuals contributing to the study, highlighting the importance of considering diverse perspectives and experiences in the analysis and interpretation of the findings.

Table 3. Seminar feedback analysis

Questions	Percentage	
	Yes (%)	No (%)
1. Were the seminar objectives clearly defined?	98	2
2. Were the topics covered relevant or interesting?	98	2
Total respondents	81	

The seminar feedback analysis reveals overwhelmingly positive responses regarding the clarity of seminar objectives and the relevance and interest of the topics covered. A staggering 98% of respondents affirmed that the seminar objectives were clearly defined, indicating a strong alignment between the organizers' intentions and the attendees' understanding. Similarly, an equal percentage of respondents found the topics covered to be both relevant and interesting, indicating that the content resonated well with the audience's interests or professional needs. With a total of 81 respondents contributing to the feedback, these high percentages reflect a widespread satisfaction among attendees with the structure and content of the seminar. These findings suggest that the organizers effectively communicated the purpose of the seminar and curated content that resonated with the audience, resulting in a successful and engaging event.

Table 4. Suggestion to make the training workshop better

Qualitative Statements
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To conduct more webinars that can help our university in terms of safety and security of the university
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I hope there would be more timely webinar like this one. Thank you
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More capacity trainings and seminar
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More training to come po
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need more time, more po, God bless po
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More time allocated
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Very good content
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More time allocated
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve audio and at least have a 5-minute quick break in between topics. This will help and relax the listener/participants to properly engage in the webinar activity later on.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Orientation of duties and responsibilities of each member; values formation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Before the webinar, request a copy of the resource persons' presentation for backup just in case they will encounter tech problem. Thank you!
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply and be ready for any eventually (in campus).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct campus safety seminars
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regularly conduct campus safety seminars

• make it periodic
• Excellent!
• More engagement for open forum (Q&A)
• Hope there would be an actual training in handling an active shooter
• I think an actual training po should follow after this webinar on properly handling an untoward situation. Thank you so much po for the knowledge and experiences that were shared by the speakers. God bless po.
• Thank you and congratulations. Maybe it's good to have a sequel: specific protocol for the campus in case of occurrence of shooting incidents
• Simulation/orientation with actual scenario and enhancement training
• I suggest we need table top drill and actual simulation, training on how to handle and manage the actual incident
• Face to face seminar
• I hope that the next capacity building would be on face-to-face appearance rather than webinar
• Must better to actual seminar
• More webinars
• Hope for the next capacity building would be in face-to-face appearance

The feedback provided in Table 4 suggests various improvements to enhance the quality and effectiveness of the seminar. Several participants emphasized the need for more webinars focusing on safety and security measures for the university, indicating a collective desire for further educational sessions in this area. Timeliness was also highlighted, with participants expressing gratitude for the current webinar and suggesting more timely events in the future. Capacity-building activities and seminars were recommended for additional training opportunities. Participants stressed the importance of allocating more time for the sessions to allow for better engagement and understanding of the content. Suggestions were made to improve audio quality and incorporate short breaks between topics to enhance participant relaxation and engagement. Additionally, there were calls for more interactive elements such as open forums and Q&A sessions to facilitate dialogue and learning. Some participants proposed practical training sessions, including handling active shooter situations, and suggested conducting campus safety seminars regularly. A preference was also expressed for face-to-face seminars over webinars, highlighting a desire for more interactive and hands-on learning experiences. Overall, the feedback underscores a strong interest in ongoing education and practical training related to campus safety and security.

2.) Campus Active Shooter Workshop and Table Top Exercise (25 May 2023)

A total of 40 confirmed participants. The attendance consisted of a mix of faculty, researchers, admin staff, and contractual personnel. A total of 30 evaluation forms were collected at the end of the seminar. However, not all participants answered the question of item # 3.

Overall, the seminar was well rated and judged very useful. The most appreciated aspects of the table top exercise were the objectives of the activity clearly defined and were the topics covered relevant. The percentage ratings from the answers to the questions related to the content of the seminar are given in the table below.

Table 5. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	22	72%
Female	18	68%
Total	30	100%

The demographic profile of respondents for the campus active shooter workshop and table top exercise conducted on April 27, 2023, indicates a slightly higher participation of males, comprising 72% of the total respondents, compared to females, who accounted for 68%. Among the 30 individuals surveyed, 22 were male and 18 were female. This distribution suggests a notable presence of both genders in the workshop and exercise, with males marginally outnumbering females. Understanding the gender composition of participants provides valuable insights for tailoring future workshops or exercises to ensure inclusivity and effectiveness across diverse demographic groups.

Table 6. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of job

Job Title	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Faculty	5	16.7%
Researcher	1	3.3%
Admin	18	60%
Contractual	6	20%
Total	30	100%

The demographic profile of participants for the campus active shooter workshop and tabletop exercise held on April 27, 2023, revealed a diverse representation across various job titles. Among the respondents, the majority were administrative staff, constituting 60% of the total participants. This highlights the significance of administrative roles within the campus community concerning emergency preparedness and response. Following administrative staff, faculty members represented 16.7% of the participants, indicating their involvement and interest in enhancing campus safety measures.

Additionally, contractual staff comprised 20% of the respondents, emphasizing the importance of including individuals from different contractual positions in such training events. Notably, researchers constituted a smaller percentage, at 3.3%, suggesting potential areas for increased engagement or outreach efforts in future workshops. Overall, the distribution of job titles among the participants underscores the collaborative effort across various sectors of the campus community towards fostering a safer environment and preparedness for unforeseen emergencies like active shooter incidents.

Table 7. Suggestions that would make the training workshop better

Qualitative Statements
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Great job
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More seminar about psychological aspect
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More seminar/ trainings for awareness and info for everyone
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learned something new, more dissemination needed for this topic
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The workshop was executed smoothly
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The speakers are experts in their field
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In my humble opinion when drafting the emergency plan, entrance, exits and emergency exits in every building should be revisited
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There should be a move to restore them to their usability as there could be a possible risk of life involved if ever there is an active shooter on campus. Thank you
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct of consultation meeting/s between the safety and security office and the safety committee to develop protocols for the subject incident

The feedback collected regarding suggestions for improving the seminar reflects a mix of positive reinforcement and constructive criticism. Participants commended the organizers for their efforts, acknowledging the seminar's overall effectiveness. Suggestions for improvement included a desire for more seminars focusing on the psychological aspects of emergencies, indicating a recognition of the importance of addressing mental health considerations in emergency preparedness. Additionally, there was a call for increased awareness and information dissemination for all members of the campus community, highlighting a desire for broader accessibility to safety resources and training.

Importantly, there was a recommendation to revisit and potentially enhance emergency plans, specifically emphasizing the need to ensure the functionality of entrances, exits, and emergency exits across campus buildings to mitigate risks in the event of an active shooter scenario. This feedback underscores a proactive approach towards refining emergency protocols and fostering collaboration between safety offices and committees to develop comprehensive incident response protocols.

3.) Simulation Drills and Exercise on Campus Active Shooter Response (September 28, 2023)

This simulation activity is the first of its kind in the Province of Laguna according to the Provincial Disaster Risk Reduction Management Office of Laguna who witnessed the said activity and the first UP constituent university to conduct it. The simulation exercise is in line with the crisis and emergency program aimed at practicing coordination and communication when confronted with an active shooter or shooting incident inside the campus.

There are three (3) scenarios in the simulation, which are as follows:

Scenario 1

A week before the class opens, students and admin staff prepare for a special activity. Two hours later, three (3) unidentified individuals in front of the School of Environmental Science and Management (SESAM) building opened fire.

Bystanders begin fleeing from the SESAM perimeter building and disperse in all directions. The perpetrator leaves the right wing of the building and proceeds to the other side, the sound of popping noises, gunshots, and screaming continues. Two (2) bystanders were killed, injured two (2) admin staff, and one (1) graduate student hostage.

Police arrive on the scene 15 minutes after the initial emergency contact. The police rushed into the building. The two (2) of the perpetrators easily surrendered upon seeing the police officers, but the other one was forced to take one student hostage. The police are now starting to use its strategic tactics to help in the hostage negotiation process.

Scenario 2

Luckily, successful negotiation from the expertly trained hostage negotiator de-escalates the situation. Law enforcement confirm that the threat is neutralized. Injured victims will now be transported to healthcare facilities and hospitals.

Scenario 3

National and local media outlets begin providing coverage of the shooting. Rumors start on social media that there are multiple shooters and multiple shooting locations. Parents begin arriving at the campus. The campus administrators assure the public that everything is now under control.

Table 8. Theme and sub-theme for simulation drills and exercise on campus active shooter response

Theme	Sub-theme
Crisis Preparedness	Simulation exercise
	First of its kind in the Province of Laguna
	Aimed at practicing coordination and communication
	Specific focus on active shooter response
	Incident description

Scenario 1: Active Shooter Incident	Unidentified individuals open fire near SESAM building
	Bystanders flee; casualties and hostage situation arise
	Response and intervention
	Police arrival and engagement
	Perpetrators' surrender and hostage negotiation
Scenario 2: Post-Incident Response	De-escalation and neutralization
	Successful negotiation and confirmation of threat status
	Transport of injured victims to healthcare facilities
Scenario 3: Media and Public Response	Media coverage and public perception
	National and local media coverage
	Social media rumors and parental concerns
	Reassurance and communication
	Campus administrators' reassurance to the public
	Confirmation of situation under control

Table 8 presents valuable suggestions aimed at improving the training experience, reflecting the participants' input on areas of potential enhancement. These suggestions serve as constructive feedback to optimize future iterations of the event, ensuring its effectiveness in preparing individuals for active shooter scenarios on campus. Meanwhile, Table 8 delineates the overarching theme and sub-themes for the simulation drills and exercise on campus active shooter response, held on September 28, 2023. The theme, crisis and emergency preparedness, underscores the importance of proactive measures in mitigating the impact of crises. This theme outlined three distinct scenarios, each focusing on critical aspects of response and intervention during an active shooter incident. Scenario 1 delves into the initial response to the crisis, highlighting the coordination and communication necessary among stakeholders, including law enforcement and emergency services. Scenario 2 emphasizes post-incident actions, such as de-escalation and medical assistance, crucial for restoring safety and aiding victims. Finally, Scenario 3 addresses the broader societal implications, including media coverage and public perception, underscoring the importance of effective communication and reassurance from campus administrators. Overall, the thematic framework and scenario-based approach provide a comprehensive platform for participants to engage in realistic simulations, thereby enhancing their preparedness and response capabilities in the face of potential threats.

Table 10. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	17	63%
Female	7	26%
Prefer Not to Say	3	11%
Total	27	100%

The demographic profile of participants in the simulation drills and exercise on campus active shooter response conducted on September 28, 2023, sheds light on the gender distribution among respondents, revealing potential avenues for enhancing training inclusivity. The majority of participants identified as male, comprising 63% of the total respondents. In contrast, female representation accounted for 26%, indicating a notable gender gap in attendance. Additionally, 11% of respondents preferred not to disclose their gender. This suggests a need for strategies to encourage greater participation from female individuals and create a more inclusive environment for all attendees. Implementing targeted outreach campaigns or providing specific resources tailored to address concerns or barriers that may deter female participation could enhance the training's effectiveness. Moreover, offering open dialogue and feedback sessions opportunities may help address any underlying issues contributing to gender disparities and ensure a more representative and diverse participant pool in future simulation drills and exercises.

Table 11. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of job

Job Title	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Faculty	0	0%
Researcher	0	0%
Admin	20	74%
Contractual	7	26%
Total	27	100%

The data from the simulation drills and exercise on campus active shooter response, conducted on September 28, 2023, highlighted valuable insights regarding the demographic profile of the participants and their suggestions for improving the training. Notably, administrative staff comprised the majority of respondents, accounting for 74% of the total participants. This indicates a strong administrative presence in the campus safety and emergency response discussion. Conversely, faculty members and researchers did not participate in the survey, suggesting potential areas for outreach to engage these groups in future trainings to ensure a more comprehensive representation of the campus community. Additionally, contractual staff accounted for 26% of the respondents, underscoring the importance of including individuals from various employment arrangements in discussions and planning related to active shooter preparedness. The absence of faculty and researchers in the feedback pool indicates a

need for targeted efforts to involve these stakeholders in future events, thereby enriching the dialogue and strategies for enhancing campus safety measures.

Table 12. Evaluation of training/seminar/workshop sessions

Questions					
	Outstanding (%)	Very Satisfactory (%)	Satisfactory (%)	Unsatisfactory (%)	Poor (%)
How would you rate the quality of the active shooter preparedness seminar?	59%	37%	4%		
How did you find the design of the lecture materials or modules?	59%	41%			
How would you rate the way the active shooter simulation exercise is organized and delivered?	70%	30%			
Overall, how would you rate your overall learning experience?	68%	32%			

The analysis of Table 12, evaluating the simulation drills and exercise on campus active shooter response conducted on September 28, 2023, reveals predominantly positive feedback regarding the training session. Notably, 59% of respondents rated the quality of the session as outstanding, indicating a high level of satisfaction with the content and delivery. Similarly, the design of the training materials or modules received favorable ratings, with 59% of respondents finding them outstanding. Moreover, the organization and delivery of the training session were highly praised, with 70% of participants rating it as outstanding, reflecting the effectiveness of the instructional approach and logistics. Overall, the learning experience garnered positive responses, as 68% of respondents

rated it as outstanding. While the majority of feedback was positive, there is minimal room for improvement, as indicated by the small percentages in the satisfactory and unsatisfactory categories for some questions. This analysis suggests that the simulation drills and exercise on campus active shooter response were generally well-received and effective in meeting the participants' learning needs, with potential for further enhancements to ensure continued excellence in future sessions.

Table 13. Suggestions that would make the training workshop better

Qualitative Statements
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I heard that this is the first simulation of active shooter response in the province. Congratulations, Great job!
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The training was informative and can help for the unexpected scenario that the university may experience
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Okay na okay po ito para sa unibersidad. Marami pa po sanang simulations and maconduct. Keep it up!
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thank you, great job!
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thank you!
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good job!
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You may also present this simulation to other offices
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More seminars/ trainings for awareness of everyone
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Okay and satisfied ang simulation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Okay ang ganitong experience dahil nalaman namin kung anong gagawin kapag nangyari ito sa totoong buhay
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good experience!

Participants of the simulation drills and exercise on campus active shooter response, conducted on September 28, 2023, provided valuable feedback and suggestions aimed at enhancing the seminar experience. Among the suggestions, there was widespread appreciation for the initiative, with participants acknowledging it as the first active shooter response simulation in the province and commending the organizers for their efforts. Many expressed satisfactions with the informative nature of the training, highlighting its relevance in preparing for unforeseen emergencies within the university setting. Some attendees also emphasized the importance of conducting more simulations in the future, underscoring the value of hands-on experience in crisis preparedness. Additionally, participants suggested extending the reach of the seminar by presenting it to other university offices and organizing more seminars or trainings to raise awareness among the entire campus community. Overall, the feedback provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of the seminar and offered constructive suggestions for its improvement, reflecting a collective commitment to enhancing campus safety and preparedness.

DISCUSSION

The summary of findings shows that in terms of sex, there were more male participants (77.8%) than female participants (19.8%), with a small percentage (2.4%) choosing not to disclose their sex. Regarding job titles, most respondents were in administrative roles (67.9%), followed by contractual workers (14.8%), faculty (11.1%), and researchers (6.2%). Feedback from the seminar attendees indicates high satisfaction with the clarity of seminar objectives (98%) and the relevance of topics covered (98%). Suggestions for improvement included conducting more webinars, increasing training opportunities, and allowing more time for sessions. For the campus active shooter workshop and tabletop exercise, most participants were male (72%) and held administrative positions (60%). Feedback on the event was positive, with attendees finding the objectives clearly defined and the topics relevant. Suggestions for improving the training included providing more training on psychological aspects, and revisiting emergency plans for campus buildings. In the simulation drills and exercise on campus active shooter response, the majority of participants were male (63%) and held administrative positions (74%). Feedback indicated high satisfaction with the training session quality (59% outstanding) and organization (70% outstanding). Suggestions for improvement included conducting more simulations, presenting the simulation to other offices, and organizing more seminars or trainings for awareness. Overall, participants found the experience informative and valuable for preparing for real-life scenarios.

Conclusions

The study aimed to evaluate participant perceptions, operational challenges, strategies employed, and learning outcomes using the methodology of the HSEEP of the US-DHS.

The findings of this study offered valuable insights to campus administrators regarding the necessity to review existing policies, training programs, drills, and exercises to enhance overall institutional security. The references cited provide additional context, including incidents of active shooter events in the Philippines and relevant methodologies in homeland security exercises.

The study revealed a predominance of male participants across all activities, particularly in administrative roles. Despite this demographic skew, participants expressed satisfaction with the events and provided constructive feedback for improvement. The seminar was commended for its clarity and relevance, while the active shooter workshop and simulation drills were praised for their objectives and organization. Suggestions for enhancement included improving psychological training, and conducting more simulations and awareness sessions. Overall, participants found these experiences valuable for enhancing preparedness for real-life scenarios.

Recommendations

Based on the feedback, here are some recommendations:

1. **Diverse Participation:** Encourage diverse participation, including more women and individuals from various roles across the campus community, to ensure a well-rounded perspective during the workshop and exercise.
2. **Enhanced Psychological Training:** Incorporate enhanced psychological training modules to equip participants with the necessary skills to manage stress and trauma effectively during crisis situations.
3. **Interactive Simulations:** Increase the number of interactive simulations during the table top exercise to offer practical, hands-on experience for participants, facilitating better understanding and crisis preparedness for real-life scenarios.
4. **Increased Awareness Sessions:** Conduct additional awareness sessions to raise understanding and preparedness levels among participants regarding active shooter situations and emergency protocols.
5. **Policy Review:** Campus administrators should also review the existing policy where applicability of the new threat shall now be included as a new policy.

Implementing these recommendations aims to enhance the effectiveness and impact of the campus active shooter workshop and table top exercise, fostering a safer and more resilient campus community.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms the ethical standards.

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